

**EFFECTIVE METHODS IN THE PROCESS OF PREPARING FUTURE PRIMARY
SCHOOL TEACHERS TO TEACH BASED ON THE PIRLS INTERNATIONAL
ASSESSMENT PROGRAM****Turanova Iroda Egamberdi qizi**

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Abstract. *The article discusses the requirements of the PIRLS international assessment program, assessment criteria, and tasks designed to prepare for international assessment programs on topics presented in new generation textbooks. At the same time, our research provides information on methods for developing primary school students' skills in understanding the content of the text, understanding the information provided in it, and imagining events not mentioned in the text based on this information.*

Keywords: *PIRLS, understanding the content of the text, primary school students, effective methods, test, imagination.*

The fundamental essence of the modernization of primary education is to familiarize young schoolchildren with the achievements and information resources of world civilization on a global scale, to organize the educational process in cooperation with teachers, students, and parents. The training of competitive personnel related to the implementation of the development of a new Uzbekistan, the creation of conditions for high-quality education for primary school students, which is one of the main links of continuous education, the selection of teaching methods, methods and tools that ensure the acquisition of knowledge, and their application in the educational process are of great importance in developing students' conscious reading skills and forming the skills to connect the acquired knowledge with practice.

In the current global globalization, due to the widespread introduction of innovative pedagogical technologies into the education system, the realization of students' creative abilities through the formation of logical, analytical, critical and independent thinking skills is an important aspect of developmental education in raising the younger generation to the level of meeting the requirements of world standards. In particular, the implementation of the PIRLS requirements for monitoring literacy in primary grades (The Progress in International Reading Literacy Study) places a great responsibility on reading education.

American researchers Elizabeth Ann, S. Kelly, who conducted research on international assessment programs and their impact on the educational process, analyzed the factors affecting student achievement internationally in their scientific research. The social background and living conditions of students have a great influence on their effective learning, while the school environment, teacher qualifications and teaching technology, and the richness of school resources are listed as the main influencing factors.

Ozyildirim Gulnar emphasized in her research that the correct organization of homework is important for students to achieve academic success. That is, homework assigned to the student in accordance with the student can be the basis for the student to achieve successful results in international assessment programs. PIRLS is carried out in accordance with the unified guidelines and rules developed by the International Assessment Research Coordination Center. Each stage of this process (sampling, translation, pilot testing, data verification and processing) is monitored by international experts.

As is known, under the PIRLS program, students are assessed for their reading skills in two types of reading: during the lesson and outside of school. This includes:

- a) determining the level of reading in order to study the experience of mastering the literary education system;
- b) determining the level of reading in terms of mastering and using the information provided in the educational process.

In the PIRLS study, students are required to have the following skills in evaluating and critically analyzing the text:

- assessing the accuracy and completeness of the information provided in the text;
- assessing the likelihood of the described event occurring in reality;
- assessing the accuracy of the author's thoughts in changing people's ideas and actions;
- assessing how much the title of the text sheds light on the main text;
- understanding language features such as metaphor and tone of speech;
- determining the author's views on the main topic.

Reading books at home, in parallel with what students, especially primary school students, learn in class, and the joint efforts of parents in this process are important in developing students' conscious reading skills and expanding their knowledge.

It is clear that the reading skills developed in primary school students' reading lessons are not enough to accept the reforms being carried out in the education system today and to participate in studies assessing students' reading skills worldwide and record high results.

After all, the main goal of students' reading is not to increase their reading speed, but to understand the content of the text being taught, to understand the main idea, and to be able to draw practical conclusions on a given topic.

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